

Panchayat Raj Institutions and Empowerment of Dalit Women in Rural India

B .Vijaya Bharatha Lakshmi

Lecturer in political Science, Smt kandukuri Rajyalakshmi Govt Degree College for Women

DOI-

Abstract

Achieving the empowerment of Dalit women is one of the progressive reforms brought on by local authorities in India. However, ongoing heterogeneity focuses on the disproportionate representation of women from diverse cultures and caste classes. While the emancipation of Dalit women (the most marginalized and impoverished segment of Indian society) is an important human rights problem in itself, in the face of a world afflicted by caste politicization, it also facilitates the realization of a multitude of other associated human rights associated with the same caste community. Dalit women's democratic voice and decision-making capacity in essential facilities, economic growth and social justice are crucial factors in questioning and changing systemic caste class segregation towards their substantive inclusion and allowing them to understand their constitutional rights. Political involvement in this regard often requires the attention of the state and the increasing role of non-state players in ensuring and respecting equitable political voice and social appreciation for these women. It involves a restructuring in power ties both within the structures of municipal government and within the grassroots social setting. In this regard, the paper argues that India has given ample room for grassroots women's political empowerment by offering a quota concept in the concept of local governance. Yet, to increase, stabilize and grow on an equitable footing, challenging the fractured Indian social framework, it is essential to evaluate and locate the empowerment problem of Dalit women through a het.

Keywords: Panchayat, Dalit Women, empowerment, perspectives, liberal, heterogeneity, consequence, societal transformation, constitution.

Introduction:

Between human rights in India or elsewhere in the world, the most critical problem is the heterogeneity of problems related to the rights of every unique social community in the specific sense of space and time. The human rights tale of Dalit women in India is not that different. As far as the Dalit group is concerned, this group has endured oppression and violence and has left it vulnerable on various fronts: religious, economic and political. While the tradition of untouchability has been abolished by statute in India, the civility of caste is still a remote illusion and missing from culture, both: Dalit men and women survive further violence at the end of the day. In this sense, several- time to measures have been taken by the government to resolve issues relevant to the oppressed section and, in particular, the Dalit community, including the reservation of women's seats, the Scheduled Tribes (STs) and the Scheduled Castes (SCs) are among the path-breaking initiatives. With many of the renovated and newly introduced features of the Panchayati Raj Institutions (hereinafter the PRIs) following the 73rd Amendment Act, the most ground-breaking in terms of gender equity and the representation of women and the weaker group of women is the allocation of 33 per cent of the seats for women and SCs and STs about their population in the village at all three stages. When these protections are implemented, a new collection of problems become present. It has begun to obstruct the execution of these protections and leave the aim partly fulfilled. These problems have become especially burdensome for downtrodden women, such as Dalits and tribal, to question their involvement in political life.

Comparatively, it is more urgent for Dalit community women to face oppression on several fronts: caste, class and gender. Since the paper deals with the empowerment of Dalit people, it is essential to understand why Dalit women need special attention when dealing with their empowerment.

Dalit Women and Serious Abuse:

Dalit women make up a large proportion of the Indian community. As a different social group, it is essential to discuss the concerns of this particular social group in the context of unique forms of oppression and abuse. In this sense, the grassroots PRIs may be seen as an emancipatory phase. Dalit women may then be elected to a women's seat and a scheduled caste seat. But the argument is that as the most vulnerable social category in society, a Dalit woman carries the brunt of all three differences: caste, class, and gender. A Dalit woman is faced with a particular type of abuse that results in socioeconomic and political insecurity. Consequently, she typically loses the effort to hit the forum to contest the elections. If she is elected somehow, she is the target of normal grassroots activities such as sarpanch-pati and panchayat pati, where on behalf of her husband's husband's serves as a sarpanch or other roles, whatever the case might be. From Ruth Manorama's study on violence against Dalit women in Hague, several instances of violence against Dalit women in rural areas can be addressed here. Traditionally, these forms of abuse are reserved for Dalit people. It includes: intense verbal harassment and sexual epithets, nude procession, dismemberment, forced urine and faeces, branding, teeth removal, tongue and nails, and crime, including murder after witchcraft has

been declared. Dalit women are often targeted by rape as part of higher-ranking collective abuse, but Dalit women and girls are also sexually abused and raped within their groups. The devadasi (or jogini) forced temple prostitution scheme is the most severe type of slavery for Dalit people. Despite its magnitude and frequency, most incidents of violence against Dalit women are not reported. The shortage of law enforcement has left many. Dalit women are reluctant to approach the justice system to pursue redress. As women are mostly ignorant of the rules, their confusion is readily abused by their critics, the police and the judiciary. Even after the cases are reported, the absence of due examination or the judge's case and gender prejudice will contribute to acquittal. The plight of Dalit women requires specific consideration. Dalit women are one of the biggest socially isolated communities in the world: they make up more than 2% of the world's total population. Three times, they are discriminated against: they are poor, women, and Dalits. While both Dalit men and women suffer from the same conventional taboos, Dalit women are more frequently faced with these. They are discriminated against not only by people of higher castes but also in their own families, where men are powerful. Consequently, Dalit women have less influence within the Dalit movement itself. While they are involved in significant numbers, most leadership roles in organizations, civic bodies and societies have been occupied by men. Addressing the human rights of Dalit women would strengthen their skills, which would contribute to their complete growth. Democratization of empowerment that is part of collective control is what the quota of women in PRIs is. Studies in various countries of the world have confirmed that, despite the requirements of affirmative action and the quota rendered to the men and women of the Scheduled Castes, their political status has not reached a degree where they can be assumed to be able to work comparatively separately, as opposed to being able to function independently. Proxies or orders from influential persons in the villages, In reality, an analysis by Leiten and Srivastava suggests that their Jat respondents in Uttar Pradesh claimed that if the citizens of the Scheduled Castes were pradhans of panchayats, this would lead to an "inversion of the normal social order" The condition of the woman members who are elected presidents by Women's delegates are ill of gender problems, and this can be seen in their working as complete members of the panchayats. Dalit women typically controlled my men from their kin, caste, and other influential groups in the villages.

Dalit Women And Panchayats:

There is an account of the Dalit women addressed by Professor Niraja Gopal Jayal concerning the

empowerment of Dalit women through these PRIs; a Dalit sarpanch, Gundiyabai Ahirwar, of Pipra Village in the Tikamgarh District of Madhya Pradesh lifted the national flag in her village on Independence Day, which was prevented from conducting this ceremonial duty because the majority of Yadav in the village felt that In India, women face the responsibility of landless farm labour, a condition born out of deprivation and hardship. Consequently, the maximum percentages of female job participation of 45 per cent and 38 per cent are for advisai and Dalit people, respectively, as a whole, just 30 per cent are incomparable to the percentage mentioned above. Around the same time, these women are exposed to sexism, harassment and sexual exploitation by the upper strata and earn less than the legally prescribed salaries. There are gaps in the educational prospects and food consumption of boys and girls in their households. Whether it is the general command that they are elected to power or their willingness to engage in panchayat decision-making processes, it is no wonder that the condition of the Dalits in the panchayats has not been of a higher order. Studies on the various states of the world have shown that Dalits always take orders as representatives from the individuals of the ruling castes and groups. Thus it will not be correct to assume that they have achieved a stage where they can work comparatively independently. Fair citizenship and political deepening are the direct implications of the freedom to vote. Both the creation of political parties and the electoral mechanism represent the heavy involvement of Dalits in politics and their confidence in democratic structures and processes. Surviving a confrontation with the colonial and post-colonial states and mainstream political parties is the tale of Dalit's fight for equitable citizenship rights. To be part of the inner truth of the Hindu society. What was deemed pure and private by the Hindu political establishment stood in direct contrast with the Dalits' claim to citizenship? The devolution of control has generated a central political area that was historically missing. Its implementation has given birth to a new dynamic in the rural policy framework and has given rise to a new revolutionary rural policy. Political empowerment born out of special arrangements for the oppressed sector, such as Dalits, Adivasis and women, has led to the rise of participatory democracy in rural society, which in turn has led to the empowerment of Dalit women by PRIs.

Four states have a 50 per cent reservation for women in PRIs: Bihar, Uttarakhand, Madhya Pradesh and Himachal Pradesh. The UPA government has also rendered the same law as the 110th amendment and approved the Bill in line with the Standing Committee on Rural Growth

requirements. The Bill was first presented in Lok Sabha in November 2009 and followed the committee procedure. Efforts were again made and re-introduced in 2010 in the Lok Sabha after a study had been presented, but sadly it lapsed in 2014 at the end of the 15th Lok Sabha. In 2016, Birender Singh, Minister of Rural Growth, called for a constitutional change to raise the women's quota in PRIs from 33% to 50%. Some other reforms expressed by the Minister have been to reserve a separate ward for a continuous duration of two terms of five years so that development work can be carried out on a continuous basis⁴⁶ This enhanced room for women in Panchayats can expand the platform for their involvement in several ways and capacities.

Nature of Women's Participation:

To understand the effect of PRIs on women's empowerment and advancement, it is essential to have a prior understanding of how PRIs help empower Dalit women while at the same time promising their promotion and demanding their reserved representation in elected bodies. The deeply stratified rural culture on the lines of caste status and gender indicates that the marginalisation of women is not based exclusively on gender but rather on the intersection of caste, class and race. That gender contributes to their subordinate role. In the rural Indian sense, however, women are marginalised, in addition to their caste, by class locations. It hinders their engagement since the higher the stratification of culture, the more levels of women there are. Due to the reservation of seats in PRIs, women will engage in political activities and become elected members of panchayats in different capacities.

The strong presence of informal networks is a central concern in the development of municipal government. These are the typical popular communities that reside in any village. These classes existed and enjoyed supremacy and a voice in decision-making in all matters relating to any state issue. But in situations, specific networks often pose problems that are impossible to resolve. Informal organisations are used as a challenge to be mitigated rather than a power to be harnessed. It has been shown that specific organisations are troublesome since the word governance incorporates organisations rather than mere executives. Therefore, looking at the broader field of governance, including society and the economy, informal institutions and contingent on them shadow institutions, it is necessary to take charge of them, 'latently, if not visibly. These organisations are the cause of injustice in the local rural governance structure. Shadow government networks are not associated with Raab and Milward's Dark Networks or Cartier-Bresson's Exploitation Networks which

are sources of illegal and antisocial activity. Problems such as lack of transparency, faith, arbitrariness, power imbalances, lack of communication, etc., are core concerns that stand in the way of a stable and easy public service delivery system.

Coordination and hence a state of equilibrium must be preserved to produce better outcomes. The superimposition of political structures and the absence of familiarity with the social condition is a significant explanation for the breakdown of the mechanisms and methodologies involved in establishing a local government in India. Whereas informal local government structures are usually intercaste structures, have "functional support" and "progressive support" as well as "oppressive proprietary characteristics and are not linearly diminishing or decreasing in the face of either modernity in general or increasingly modern elected local councils in particular. Instead, they communicate, sometimes in a constructive way, with these structured municipal government structures.

Participation And Empowerment:

Empowerment is primarily related to words such as capacity, engagement and growth, where both meanings are interdependent and interconnected. PRIs transparent forums for women to maintain their opinions on decision-making and allow them to take decisions on the position of women sarpanch. Higher-level engagement by citizens is a medium for transparency and one of the fundamental characteristics of democratic governance. Conscious decisions should be taken on subjects of interest to public existence, and facilitating those decisions should be consulted. Knowledge would allow citizens to make those decisions. Informal citizenship is thus the central democracy; otherwise, democracy will not fulfil its function and will exist theoretically without any realistic applicability. Indeed, the state's funding for welfare and wellbeing programmes may be strengthened and measured by the extent of participation. Empowerment is a term that originated with the empowerment of women in the 1960s. The word has increasingly been identified with topics such as civil society, association and organization. It is now at the core of every debate that stresses the involvement of the vulnerable in development. Historically, the idea of empowerment has been examined mainly from two perspectives: the person where 'psychological empowerment is studied' and, secondly, 'individual empowerment.' Knowledge is a catalyst to engaged citizenship and engagement, societal transformation, and lifelong learning. Knowledge is essential to help maintain a democratic society. Feminism, Theology, Freudian Psychology, the Black Power Revolution, and Gandhism in India are some of the trends that arose

as landmarks of the usage of the word liberation later on. At the expense of redundancy, the word undoubtedly first appeared in the feminist and progressive debates of the 1980s and eventually became used and inspired by the revolutionary vocabulary of International. Empowerment applies to values such as the capacity of people and communities to intervene to maintain their well-being or the freedom to engage in decision-making that affects them. The much-praised work of Barbara Solomon, "Black Empowerment: Social Service in the Disadvantaged Groups," gives way to the use of a phrase restricted to the United States (US) before the 1970s with an emphasis on the vulnerable and marginalised, there was a great deal of presence in study and policy formulation. The word has now acquired enough presence in social care providers and social protest campaigns of various kinds. The past of term empowerment in the construction lexicon has its formal presence in the feminist revolution that started in the global south with the emergence of DAWN (Construction Alternatives with Women for a New Era), established in the city of India in 1984. Following the row, after the celebrated work, "Empowerment: The Strategy of Alternative Growth" by John Freidman, published in 1992, the emphasis on the idea of Empowerment eventually changed to empowering the disadvantaged. Friedman was the first to shift the focus of the concept of Empowerment to the underprivileged. Indeed, the word was blamed for its fluidity. However, the term "women empowerment" has traditionally been defined in most policy papers. While used in various ways, such as democratisation and decentralisation, the word lacks clear reference and remains loosely defined. From 1960 to 1980, creation and growth models have been debated and examined for almost two decades. Values such as fairness and democracy have been granted priority in terms of political concerns. And the word empowerment has been established, "Giving control to a specific unprivileged segment of society. The Empowerment of Dalit women is a severe problem given the kind of oppression and abuse recorded in different media. The Empowerment of Dalit women by PRIs will prove promising and help to control the number of cases of prejudice and harassment. It was a tragedy that Dalit women faced discrepancies from different directions. There is a tiny room for Dalit women in the Dalit movement itself. As a consequence of this, Dalit women slip into the category of the most marginalized social community.

Conclusion:

However, the PRI idea brought about a progressive change given the challenges and concerns connected with the Consumer Panchayats Institutions before

the entry into force of the 73rd Amendment Act. The essence of Dalit women's engagement is still fractured through various stratification lines in society, and the study needs to be taken to the fore. Dalit women, who are among the most vulnerable groups, need to be researched from various fronts to clarify their presence in and an impediment to panchayats. As questions of a gross sort when it comes to violence against them, the multiple forms of ensuring their sufficient representation in these structures of devolution of authority must be streamlined in the form of violence, involvement and expression and, ultimately, their strong voices discussing their problems must be the elected representatives of the panchayats. More so when talking about their continuing empowerment to ensure their improved socio-economic and political standing.

1. References:

1. Ruth Manorama, "Human Rights and Dignity of Dalit Women", Report of the Conference in The Hague, 20-25 November 2006.
2. Leiten and Srivastava, Unequal Partners: Power Relations, Devolution and Development in Uttar Pradesh (New Delhi: Sage, 1999).
3. Ananad Inbanathan and N Sivanna, "Schedule castes, Legitimacy and Local Governance : Continuing Social Exclusion in Panchayats", working paper 257, Institute of Social and Economic Change, 2010.
4. NirjaGopalJoyal. "Gender and Decentralisation" Decentralization in India: Challenges and Opportunities, HDRC, UNDP, 2003.
5. Martha Nussbaum, Amrita Basu, Yasmin Tambiah and Niraja Gopal Jayal, "Essays on Gender and Governance", UNDP, 2003.
6. Ananad Inbanathan and N Sivanna, "Scheduled Castes, Legitimacy and Local Governance: Continuing Social Exclusion in Panchayats", working paper 257, Institute of Social and Economic Change, 2010.
7. Suryakant Waghmore, Civility against Caste: Dalit Politics and Citizenship in Western India, (New Delhi: Sage, 2013). 166.